

On the Body and Blood of the Lord (De corpore et sanguine Domini) - Paschasius Radbertus

By Sarah Luginbill, Trinity University

Entry tags: Christian Theology, Medieval Christianity, Catholic, Religious Group, Text

One of the earliest complete treatises on the Eucharist, Paschasius Radbertus' *De corpore* contained twenty-two chapters, each answering a specific question related to the Eucharist, and included references and excerpts from the works of the early church fathers and to scripture. Radbertus (c.785-c.865) was a Carolingian theologian and Benedictine monk at the abbey of Corbie in northern France. Around 833, Radbertus first wrote the *De corpore* and dedicated it to Warin, his former pupil and fellow monk at Corbie, who had traveled to the newly established abbey of Corvey in Saxony and become its abbot. According to Radbertus' prologue, Warin requested a short work on the Eucharist for his new community on the edge of Christendom. In late 843, shortly after Radbertus became abbot of Corbie, he revised and rededicated the *De corpore* to Charles the Bald, King of the Franks. This second edition included several miracle stories surrounding the Eucharist that did not appear in the first version, as well as a new dedicatory prologue to the king. Throughout the *De corpore*, Radbertus argued that the Eucharistic bread and wine were the literal body and blood of Christ and not merely symbols of it. Radbertus opened the entire text with a chapter explicitly about this issue. The *De corpore* also addresses specific aspects of the celebration of the Mass, including the use of ritual objects, and Old Testament precedents for Christ's suffering.

Date Range: 830 CE - 835 CE

Region: W Europe

Region tags:

Western Europe around the year 835 CE.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Paschasius Radbertus, *On the Body and Blood of the Lord*, with the Letter to Fredugard (trans. and ed. Mark Vaillancourt; Brepols 2020)
- Source 2: Paschasius Radbertus, *De corpore et sanguine Domini* (ed. Beda Paulus; Brepols, 1969)
- Source 3: Mayke de Jong, *Epitaph for an Era: Politics and Rhetoric in the Carolingian World* (Cambridge University Press, 2019)

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb
– No

Cemetery
– No

Temple
– No

Shrine
– No

Altar
– No

Devotional marker
– No

Cenotaph
– No

Church
– No

Mosque
– No

Synagogue
– No

Triumphal Arch
– No

- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - No
- ↳ Library/archive
 - Yes
- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: Possible unknown copies

Methods of Composition

– Written

- ↳ Inked
 - with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

–Other textile: Vellum

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Materiality

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Theology

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

|

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– No

↳ Illuminations?

– Yes

↳ Is there spiritual value associated with the coloration?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there gold?

– Yes

↳ Other forms of illumination?

– Specify: Generic line designs

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Theological

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: None

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

|

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– No

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

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– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

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Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

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Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

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Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

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Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

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Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Western European Christians, mostly monks and priests, across state and "national" boundaries

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No destruction or targeting of this text is noted in the historical record.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

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Public Works

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Warfare

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Bibliography

General References

Reference: On the Body and Blood of the Lord (De corpore et sanguine Domini) - Paschasius Radbertus, de Jong, Mayke. Epitaph for an Era. Cambridge University Press, 2019.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Epitaph_for_an_Era.html?hl=&id=5IKWDwAAQBAJ.

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Traditio 47 (1992): 1-36. <http://www.jstor.com/stable/27831869>.

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<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0017816010000635>.

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Zirkel, Patricia McCormick. "why Should It Be Necessary That Christ Be Immolated Daily?" - Paschasius Radbertus on Daily Eucharist". *The American Benedictine Review* 47, no. 3 (1996): 240-59.